

FORMATION OF MEDICAL TERMS AND THEIR LINGUISTIC, COMMUNICATIVE ASPECTS

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Abstract. This article provides information on the formation of medical terms. Linguistic and communicative aspects of anatomical terms, construction structure of terms and importance in medicine are discussed based on analysis with examples.

Key words: classification, adenoma, aspects, formation, branches, methods, phenom

In the last century, clinical medicine has grown into many new branches. All this happened thanks to the development of science and technology. New diagnostic tools and methods have appeared, for example, computed tomography, sonograph, mammograph, laparoscope, endoscope, colonoscope, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), etc.

New diseases have also appeared, such as AIDS, bovine spongiform encephalopathy (mad cow disease), bird flu (H5N1 virus), swine flu (H1N1 virus), etc. All these new phenomena must be named, documented and disseminated among scientists and ordinary people. Thus, new words must be formed, i.e. medical terms. How were these new words formed? What methods of term formation predominate at present? The formation of new terms in each field of medicine deserves appropriate attention because the terms are gradually becoming part of the general language.

There is a very close connection between the common (codified) language and the language of science. The language of science makes up about three-quarters of all written and printed materials in the general language. While everyone uses a common language, the language of science requires a certain level of scientific education, since terms, being names of certain concepts, indicate only their meaning. Only experts know exactly what they mean.

Most anatomical and clinical terms used in medicine today are Latin or Latinized Greek words, the origins of which can be traced back to the 5th century BC. In order for medical terminology to function effectively and be understood, the terms must be correctly formed,

derived, and pronounced correctly. Basic information on word formation and word analysis allows students to handle medical terminology more effectively. Instead of memorizing lists of terms, they can easily predict the meaning of other terms.

In medical terminology, two completely different phenomena can be observed: a very precisely developed, standardized international anatomical terminology and a rapidly developing clinical terminology in all medical fields, characterized by a certain terminological confusion. The main reason for this phenomenon is the rapid development of scientific knowledge and the need to name new devices, diseases, symptoms, etc. as quickly as possible. All attempts to unify clinical medical terminology at the international level, in general, have not been successful so far.

The first attempt to create a unified international classification of diseases was already made in the 19th century. This classification did not have uniform rules and, like today's International Classification of Diseases (ICD), is just a technical tool used for statistical purposes. The lack of a unified medical terminology is obvious especially now, when computers have entered medicine and impeccable international communication is required.

From a linguistic point of view, the study of clinical terminology is much more interesting due to its variability and colorfulness. Many of the examples in this article are taken from hematology because it is a relatively young branch of medicine. This terminology is in the process of development, thanks to which many interesting phenomena can be traced. The material for this study was terms and terminological phrases, microtexts defining basic medical concepts, which were selected using a continuous sampling method from scientific articles related to various subject areas of medicine, including hematology, dictionaries, and Internet sites dedicated to medicine. This study required the integrated use of methods and techniques used in modern linguistics.

Methods of linguistic analysis, such as the descriptive method, distributive method, component analysis method, contextual analysis method and comparative method were used in processing the factual material. The components of the comparative method were comparative interpretation and typological characteristics.

Medical terms can be mainly divided into single-word terms and multi-word terms. Single-word terms can be simple (non-derivative) words, derived words, compounds of derivatives and complex words. As a rule, new vocabulary is formed for three reasons: it is spread in three possible ways:

1. The emergence of new names,
2. Formation of new meaning and
3. Borrowing words from other languages.

Some linguists divide the methods of forming new terms into groups:

1. morphological method of word formation - compounding, abbreviation;
2. syntactic, through the formation of phrases and phrases from several words;
3. semantic - narrowing (clarification) of the meaning of commonly used words;

metaphorical and metonymic transfer of previous meaning;

4. borrowing words from other languages. The most productive way of forming terms is word production. The resulting medical terms may consist of a prefix, one or two word roots and a suffix in various combinations, as presented in the following examples: myocardium = myo- (prefix) + card(ium) (root) endocarditis = endo- (prefix) + card (root) + -tis (suffix) cytology = cyt(o) (root) + -logy (suffix) gastroenterology = gastr(o) (root) + enter(o) (root) + -logy (suffix) adenoma = aden (o) (root) + oma (suffix). The second most productive type of term formation is compounding.

A compound word is a stable expression consisting of two or more stems, for example, human being (person), blood donor (blood donor), hay fever (hay fever), Black Death (plague). While in German compound words are easily recognized because they are always written together, in English the spelling of compound words varies. Phrases can be written:

1. A phrase of two/three words: blood pressure, blood group, heart attack, sleep walker, central nervous system;

2. Hyphenated: life-span (life expectancy), collar-bone (collarbone); or

3. As one word: gallstone (gallstone), haemophilia (hemophilia), leucocytopenia (leukopenia), pseudopolycytemia (pseudopolycythemia). There are no strict rules for writing difficult words. Sometimes some terms are written with a hyphen, sometimes as two different words or one word, for example, life span - life-span; gall bladder - gallbladder. The composition of compound words appears older than word production from a diachronic point of view, since derivational affixes developed from independent words.

A similar process can be seen today in the process of prefixoids (pseudo-prefixes) and suffixoids (pseudo-suffixes), for example, myo-, arthro-, haemo-lhaemato-, adipo-, hepato, onco-, patho-; -aemia, -logy, -tomy, -pathy, -cyte, -algia, -ectomy, -scope, etc. Each of these pseudo-affixes carries a specific meaning, but they are not used as independent words. They

were formed artificially from the roots of Greek and Latin words for scientific purposes - to give names to new concepts.

Although the formation of terms may seem formal and uninteresting to many people, in addition to the precise, pragmatic, structural forms of word formation, there are also many intermediate ways of forming terms that hide a whole story in their names. Sometimes a language teacher may struggle to collect, study, summarize, and even write about them, but discussing the origins of terms with medical students gives them a deeper understanding of the history of medicine and gives them the opportunity to look at certain terms from different perspectives. .

Another important point is that in teaching and practicing medicine we must be absolutely and unequivocally sure of the meaning of the terms we use. Analyzing important medical terms forces us to think about their exact meaning and be aware of any possible ambiguity. "Medical terms are very much like individual puzzles.

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